

Critical Making

D7.1 COMMUNICATION, ENGAGEMENT AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

About this document

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V., Germany
H2020	Horizon2020 – The European Research Framework Programme
OSHW	Open Source Hardware
OSH	Open Science Hardware
R&I	Research & Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TUB	Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
VTT	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY, Finland
WIF	Wikifactory Europe SL, Spain
WP	Work Package
WP1	Project Management
WP2	Building the critical making knowledge-base: concept & methods
WP3	Case Action: GENDER
WP4	Case Action: YOUNG TALENTS
WP5	Case Action: OPENNESS
WP6	Evaluation, Impact, Future Implications
WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation, Austria

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Critical Making wants to add scientific insights into the potentials of the maker movement for critical, socially responsible making, and show how these communities can offer new opportunities for young makers of all genders to contribute to an open society via open innovation. This document constitutes deliverable 7.1, Critical Making Exploitation, Dissemination, and Communication Plan in the framework of Work Package 7 (WP7). The plan presents the corresponding strategy and necessary measures to implement it.

The aim of this document is to:

- Support all consortium partners on how to disseminate information about the project to the specific target groups and identified stakeholders.
- Align the tone of voice of the project with each of the different partner's communication strategies.
- Make accessible the visual identity to be used for all communication and dissemination materials.

For the communication, engagement and dissemination plan we identify stakeholders along the quadruple helix, with a strong focus on the Civil Society actors. The events for engagement and dissemination preliminary targets have been set, but physical encounters are currently still limited due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

This document also includes a set of KPIs that we aim to achieve and those will be revisited in future deliverables and the management report.

INTRODUCTION

Critical Making adds scientific insights into the potential of the maker movement. It focuses on critical and socially responsible making, and it shows how these communities can offer new opportunities for young makers of all genders to contribute to an open society via open source innovation.

In this project, we study grassroots innovation processes taking place in open spaces (Makerspaces, Fab Labs...) and their online extensions. These initiatives will be then related to responsible research and innovation, short RRI, practices and more. We will search for and analyse existing innovation and co-design processes taking place in these open spaces to find out how far they reflect or contradict RRI principles.

A mixed-method approach will allow us to collect data, analyse it, actively improve practices, develop theories and synthesize findings. Besides analysing existing practices, we will co-design, evaluate and disseminate concrete interventions that aim to foster RRI principles in the maker movement. In three case actions, the project will specifically look at aspects of gender, openness and the recruitment of young talents.

As a result, we will co-define measures on how to better implement RRI principles in the open-source innovation movement taking place across maker communities. Our findings will provide hands-on input for practitioners in the field and will enrich the scientific knowledge base in the RRI community on innovation processes outside of academia, aiming to harness the full innovation potential of the global grassroots maker movement.

The WP7 is responsible to support all the other packages by coordinating an integrated communication and dissemination of the project's objectives, activities and results. The project has defined six main general objectives (See

Table 1) and the WP7 has aligned another six objectives related to them (See Table 1).

Table 1 Critical Making Objectives

Objective	General Objective	MP7 Objective
O1	Improve the scientific knowledge on RRI in grassroots innovations	To define and implement an integrated communication, engagement and dissemination strategy to efficiently and effectively promote the project's objectives, activities and results, in an open and accessible fashion.
O2	Increase gender awareness in maker communities	To define and develop customised approaches in collaboration with all partners and across all WPs, using a wide range of communication tools and channels, in order to effectively target key stakeholders throughout the project and across the quadruple helix
O3	Involve young people in makerspaces, increase their interest in science and innovation	To liaise with the target groups, especially from the maker community in order to reach wide visibility for the Critical Making actions.
O4	Foster responsibility in the open hardware movement	To support the engagement activities taking place across all WPs and promote the project to the wider science community, especially the RRI related community, both within Europe and internationally, in order to support and encourage uptake of the outcomes and results.
O5	Manifest grassroots innovations in the RRI discourse	To track and monitor KPIs with regards to the Communication & Engagement Plan, and Dissemination plan to maximise the

		impact of Critical Making, adapting the plans accordingly to respond to KPI progress.
O6	Elaborate guidelines and recommendations for transformative innovation policies	To promote Critical Making via targeted campaigning, awards, online and offline engagement.

This plan aims to incorporate all the objectives and be a guide to maximise the impact of Critical Making. The consortium will be seeking to reach and engage a wide community of current and future stakeholders across the quadruple helix, with a particular focus on mobilizing the maker community for our case actions. Also, it developed a visual identity and project branding of Critical Making, designed and built the project website, set up social media and community channels. It will be discussed more in the next chapter.

ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

The communication implementation will be deeply involved with all the other Work Packages.

Figure 1: Pert chart - Work Package alignment

STAKEHOLDER MAP

Our initial stakeholder map is structured around the quadruple helix. This is still a very broad view of the actors, but it should provide a first very broad and high-level overview of the different actors we may address (and engage) with our activities. We are also aware of the further developments of the

quadruple helix into a quintuple helix, which also considers the environment as a key player in the innovation ecosystem according to Carayannis (2012)¹ and other innovation scholars. But for the aim of identifying specific stakeholders, audiences and target groups for Critical Making the quadruple helix seems appropriate as the helixes, and especially the natural environment and socio-ecological contexts are considered across the actors outlined below, and especially with the civil society actors. Also, Critical Making just recently subscribed to the European Climate Pact², showing commitment towards environmental concern.

Figure 2: Critical Making Stakeholder Map

In the following we present each of these stakeholder groups in greater detail, outlining which connections we already have identified and how we want to engage them in the project:

¹ Carayannis, E. G., Barth, T. D., & Campbell, D. F. (2012). The Quintuple Helix innovation model: global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation. *Journal of innovation and entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2192-5372-1-2>

² https://europa.eu/climate-pact/index_en

Academia

Critical Making is classified as a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) according to the European funding scheme, meaning that it is foremost a research project with scientific objectives. In a participatory and transdisciplinary way, researchers and makers will study innovation processes encountered in the maker community. Thus, academia plays an important stakeholder role in this setting.

As the consortium consists of experts in the field of transformative, social innovation, grassroots innovation as well as RRI and its related topics, we clearly have a strong network we will leverage on and a growing list of related projects and initiatives via which we are planning to address and engage our academic peers. The current list of relevant **projects** (see below in the Strategic Partnerships section) are covering the different areas relevant for our research, such as RRI, digital social innovation, the maker movement and grassroots innovation as well as transformation and deliberation studies.

Individual academics from our networks that are not part of any of these projects will be approached as well, either directly or via our institutional dissemination channels.

A specific target group that we have identified in the academic sector are **Science managers and communicators** as well as **R&I and Open Science experts**. These are often experts working in central units at the interface between academic staff and administration. RRI in general, but especially Open Science, Science Communication and gender have been widely taken up by academic institutions in Europe and we find nowadays dedicated experts taking care of the implementation at the institutional level.

Government

Critical Making wants to involve policy makers at various levels. As one of the aims of the project is to introduce innovative practices to support maker skills

education, public incentives for gender inclusive measures or new regulations, and value models for Open Source Hardware. Thus, we plan to engage policy makers during the research process in different stages and across the different WPs. To ensure that policy recommendations are being taken up by policy makers we believe that an early engagement is important, and we will thus work with **local research and innovation policy managers**. For example, from the educational perspective Maja Lasić, German politician or Bündnis Freie Bildung (Free Education Alliance).

For policy makers at the EU level, we plan to hold a face-to-face encounter, either stand-alone or in the context of a larger high-level policy event in the context of WP6. In addition, specific policy briefs are foreseen.

Civil Society

As Critical Making is mostly engaging with grassroots initiatives, the wide range of actors subsumed under the term civil society are the most important stakeholders for our engagement activities. Our main stakeholder group, namely the **makers, hackers and their local, national and international communities** will be engaged from the very beginning. In a participatory approach, we will explore current practices and co-design of our interventions across the different WPs together with these stakeholders. For the specific case actions of WP3, WP4 and WP5 different subcommunities and actors will be engaged, according to the practices and interests.

Industry

In the group of actors we cannot forget industry, be it small SMEs that might be closely related to maker communities or larger enterprises, who envision or already have established collaborations with makers. E.g. the collaboration with the Open!Next project (<https://opennext.eu>) will give us access to some of these industry players, who are exploring new avenues in the field of Open Hardware. For example from the educational perspective Mekanika, a

platform offering innovative open source tools and machines, or Sono Motors a company developing Solar Electric Vehicle. And finally, we also identified media in this group of stakeholders. While we will be doing most of our communication and outreach via our institutions' media channels, there are certain players, e.g., professional journalists and media outlets (newspapers, magazines, radio), that may be important stakeholders to reach new audiences and to give new inputs.

STRATEGIC PARTNERSHIPS

Connection to relevant networks and communities

Our approach has to be inclusive, meaning putting our partners at the centre of our communications efforts. As the Critical Making stakeholder landscape is vast, we list here a few of the most important actors in the network and why they are relevant for the project:

Table 2. Relevance for Critical Making

Name	Relevance for Critical Making
RRI research community, incl. RRING http://www.rring.eu/	Advancing knowledge on RRI; engagement via the projects mentioned in Section 1.3
Open Science Hardware movement OSH & Africa OSH http://openhardware.science/	Open science network including developing countries
Fab Foundation https://fabfoundation.org/ fab.io	International network of fablabs; working on Open Hardware business models; open standards for documentation

FabLearn – Digital Fabrication in Education https://fablearn.org/	FabLearn is a network, research collaborative, and vision of learning for the 21st century.
Weizenbaum Institut: Working Group on Production Possibilities of the Maker Culture https://www.weizenbaum-institut.de/	Related research on gender, sustainability and international development and maker culture
Critical Making Consortium, Netherlands http://criticalmaking.nl/	A consortium of the Waag Society, Willem de Kooning Academy, etc with a focus on critical thinking, making and art
Open Design & Manufacturing (OD&M) https://odmplatform.eu/	OD&M is a Knowledge Alliance dedicated to creating and support communities of practices around the Open Design & Manufacturing paradigm, making the most of openness, sharing and collaboration to create new value chains of innovation in design and manufacturing oriented to the social good
Innovation for Policy Foundation (i4Policy) https://i4policy.org/	Platform for innovation community leaders in 28 African countries promoting digital innovation for inclusive and sustainable development

Relevant European-funded projects (SwafS and others)

Critical making builds on the experiences of the consortium partners, who are either involved directly in other, relevant projects or who have

established connections with projects that are of relevance for this work and where exchange and collaboration are assured. With the direct engagement of consortium partners establishing a strategic partnership, ties may be easier than in the cases where there is no direct connection. However, in a first analysis, we have also come across some projects that are of great relevance (where no consortium partner is involved) and where we would likewise try to establish a connection and start a dialogue in the course of the project. We are also aware that at the time of writing this deliverable some projects are about to finish or have already finished. However, those identified here are still offering a service to the community or continue in some way or other to exploit their results and are thus of relevance for Critical Making.

The current list of projects for potential collaboration includes the following projects:

Table 3. Relevant European-funded projects

Project	Critical making connection	Status
RRI - related projects		
ProEthics, Participatory real-life experiments in research and innovation funding organisations on ethics, https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872441	The project provides principles, guidelines, assessment criteria, good practice on ethical principles of fairness, transparency, gender, privacy and sustainability.	Ongoing project, which we will use mostly for dissemination and communication purposes and to address research funding agencies. H2020 (partner: ZSI)
CHERRIES: Constructing healthcare environments through	The project aims to create more open, inclusive and self-sustaining territorial R&I ecosystems and policies and	This is an ongoing project, where Critical Making can connect specifically with

RRI and entrepreneurship strategies, H2020 https://www.cherries2020.eu	Critical Making will exchange ideas on new innovation policies.	WP6 activities on innovation policies. (partner: ZSI)
SuperMoRRI: Scientific Understanding and Provision of an Enhanced and Robust Monitoring system for RRI, H2020 https://www.supermorri.eu/	Contribute to advance beyond the MoRRI project by developing a proper scientific understanding of the complex and diverse relationships between RRI policies and practices and their societal, democratic, economic, and scientific benefits.	ongoing project, where we want to connect Critical Making as an example of bottom-up innovation (next to the more academic view) (partner: Advisory Board member)
CoAct: Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action, H2020 https://coactproject.eu/	CoAct develops and pilots open and participatory methodologies to enable citizens and communities to co-shape structural decision making processes.	ongoing project; exchange of methodological experiences in co-design and co-evaluation is envisioned for this project; (partners: ZSI, GIG)
FRANCIS: Frugal Innovation by citizens for citizens, H2020	The project aims to build criteria and guidelines for responsible citizen engagement in open innovation and citizen - industry collaboration. Critical Making will exchange insights on RRI principles in grassroots innovations with the project.	ongoing project; exchange of experiences with regards to the applied methodologies is planned. (partner VTT)
NewHoRRizon: Excellence in Science and Innovation for Europe by adopting Responsible Research and Innovation, H2020	Learn from the social labs and the stakeholder processes for RRI topics; build on the findings on social acceptance of RRI, especially the Social labs	NewHoRRizon is about to end in June 2021 after an extension. The final event series in May will be attended by Critical Making partners as we can promote

https://newhorizon.eu/	covering industrial leadership and societal challenges.	our project and learn from their findings. (partners: VTT, ZSI)
Smart-map: supporting responsible research and innovation in selected industries, H2020 http://projectsmartmap.eu/	Build on the findings of RRI implementation and its barriers, especially in the 3D printing industry, which is one of the target industries in Smart-map.	Smart-map has recently finished, but established a community on LinkedIn. Critical Making may use this community to identify stakeholders and for dissemination purposes. (partner: ZSI)
Satori: Stakeholders acting together on the ethical impact assessment of research and innovation, FP7, https://satoriproject.eu/	The Project offers RRI tools for responsible industry and an ethics assessment framework that will be considered in our evaluation framework	finished project, but with an important resource to be considered for Critical Making. (partner: VTT)
RRI-Tools , building a better relationship between science and society FP7, https://www.rri-tools.eu/	The project has an active platform where we will share our toolbox and guidelines for critical and responsible making	official EC funding period finished, but still, a lively community around aspects of RRI and practical guidelines; RRI-Tools is an important resource and offers access to a wide community for our WP7 communication activities. (partner: ZSI)
Plotina: promoting gender balance and inclusion in research, innovation and	The project enabled the development, implementation and assessment of self-tailored Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in	finished project: For Critical Making, we want to get inspiration from gender action plans and build on

<p>training, H2020 https://www.plotina.eu/</p>	<p>Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) with innovative and sustainable strategies.</p>	<p>the experience of promoting a gender-aware culture change (partner: ZSI)</p>
<p>HubIT, Technology with and for society, H2020 https://www.hubit-project.eu</p>	<p>The hub for boosting the responsibility and inclusiveness of ICT enabled Research and Innovation through constructive interactions with SSH research.</p>	<p>recently finished project with a lot of resources for Critical Making and a wide network of actors we may engage in our activities. (partner: TUB)</p>
<p>maker - related projects</p>		
<p>Open!Next: Company-community collaboration for open source development of products and services, H2020 https://opennext.eu/</p>	<p>Open!Next supports SMEs to build better company-community collaboration in order to push co-development and market exploration in the field of Open Source Hardware (OSH) and related services and is highly relevant for WP5.</p>	<p>ongoing project; a special interest has already been expressed for our Critical Making WP5 activities; Open!Next gives us access to Open Source Hardware companies (partners: WIF, ZSI)</p>
<p>DDMP: Distributed Design Market Platform, Creative Europe Programme https://distributeddesign.eu/</p>	<p>An exchange and networking hub for the European maker movement; the distributed design principles such as openness or diversity can be aligned with the critical making principles.</p>	<p>ongoing project; offers access to a designer community that is closely related and partly overlapping with the maker community (partners: GIG, WIF)</p>
<p>DO-IT: Digital fabrication and making for social innovators, H2020</p>	<p>WP4 will build on the experiences of DO-IT in promoting entrepreneurial skills for young social innovators in an open digital world and their</p>	<p>finished project, but with a well established collaboration with some key partners. (partner: ZSI)</p>

https://doit-europe.net/	open workshops with digital tools and maker education.	
careables/Made4You: Open and inclusive healthcare for citizens based on digital fabrication, H2020 https://www.careables.org/	Careables is dealing with open source hardware in a specific field (health and care) and how this can be translated to other fields. A core project settled in the worldwide maker community.	finished the EC-funding period and has entered a new phase under the organisational structure of GIG; (partners: ZSI, GIG)
MakeIt: Understanding Collective Awareness Platforms with the Maker Movement, H2020 http://make-it.io/	One of the first projects to systematically study the maker movement in terms of governance structures, collaboration and value creation.	finished project; still, the results and some of the network partners are important for the Critical Making communication and engagement activities. (partner: ZSI)

TARGET GROUPS & CORE MESSAGES

Critical Making will reach and actively engage a diversity of target groups on local, national, and transnational level in order to achieve its objectives within the different WPs. The goal will be targeted to expand the reputation and awareness of Critical Making in:

- The scientific/academic networks with the focus on the RRI research community.
- Local or international companies that are working or show interest in developing a more critical and responsible business including any Fablab or makerspace.

- Local/Regional and EU administrations (public bodies) like city councils, public regional institutions or public organisations, that are building and implementing social policies.
- Civil society and in particular associations, NGOs, maker movements, activists, neighbours, and other local communities (including potential, future members of the maker community).

While the academic and maker communities are reached via established networks, conferences, and publication outlets, the communication activities specifically target audiences beyond the project's own community. We will target this very diversified approach via two channels – through online promotional and dissemination activities and through physical events. Scientific outcomes will be presented in the form of publications, a special edition, the participation in conferences and the integration of insights into lectures.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT THROUGH CASE ACTIONS

Gender

We aim to co-design interventions, mostly for the online space, to provide more gender diverse offers for collaboration and engagement in maker activities. So far, we have identified more than 50 case studies that relate to gender aspects in critical making, of which we will select around 15 for a deeper analysis via expert interviews. The initial contacts that are established for this analysis will be continually expanded during the **co-design activities**, aiming to link makers that are interested in gender related aspects, provide the opportunities for experience exchange based on the content and co-created interventions we develop in our project. We expect around 120 participants to be involved in the co-design measures for gender, but will also share them with the wider Wikifactory community, the worldwide GIG network, and broader partner networks, etc. Specific **stakeholder**

sustainability workshops will be organised, physically and online to share our findings and transform them into sustainable guidance for gender awareness in maker spaces.

Young Talents

We aim to connect the different stakeholder groups and invite them to take part in the co-creation of future research goals and ultimately elaborate a best practice guide to integrate young people into the maker community. 2 main events of 1-2 days with up to 60 participants have been planned to gather people and information:

1. **Critical Making Festival:** an informal event where stakeholders can meet and exchange: mixed types of sessions will allow them to share and exchange, e.g. barcamps, workshops, and even courses. Stakeholder groups include hacker- and makerspaces, schoolteachers, university students, policy makers. This event is planned to be organized in person in May 2022. Rapid tests will be made available and for those who cannot travel, we will offer blended formats.
2. **Youth Makeathon:** aligned with the “project week” of schools in Germany, this event will take place in June 2022: a Hackathon targeted at young people with the specific goal to produce a tangible object or product that addresses a societal issue, organized with the vocational education teachers of the future at the TUB. The concept is based on the TU-course on Critical Making and involves RRI principles in the ideation and project design phase.

To subsequently get continuous feedback and input, we will organize **Meet-ups** every two months following the two main events in order to enable deeper discussions on particularly relevant topics that have emerged from the main events. The meetups will take place at the university or a makerspace. They are informal get-togethers of approx. 5-8 relevant participants.

To ensure a broad involvement and success of the co-design work, TU Berlin will use its existing large network of stakeholders. The TUB has several collaborations with local and international makerspaces (local: Motionlab, X-hain, Fablab-Berlin, European: through the HubIT-network and the Critical Making consortium). Through our course “Digital Worlds” and the TUB-students of vocational education we have a substantial network of teachers that already teach making at local schools. Our educational efforts are always in close coordination with local educational providers like LISUM and Die Jungen Tüftler. Other TUB-run programs like EmoTek-Flexi and Zuper-Q successfully teach making with a focus on sustainability for students of schools in disadvantaged areas. By inviting all these actors in our network and enabling them to share their experiences, the TUB is in a unique position to get valuable feedback on the most pressing questions of the stakeholders involved with regard to the inclusion of young people into the maker community under consideration of the RRI-principles.

Openness

Through the Critical Making Open Hardware Programme we are engaging with grassroots innovation movements from the GIG network, makers and other community members of Wikifactory, project partners and the project’s advisory board to first co-design the programme itself and then to reach out to relevant target communities of the Open Source Hardware field in the next step.

The outreach to OSHW communities will take place as a global open call for RRI-informed open hardware projects that will focus on supporting the SDGs in three main target topics: open science, social innovation and environmental sustainability. We will reach the audience through the GIG network, the Wikifactory community and other networks identified in the co-design process.

Throughout the programme duration **Meet-ups** and **workshops** are organised for the registered participants to ensure engagement throughout the process. At the end of the programme a public 1-day online event (Demo Day) is organized, including a welcome note from the WP5 partners, and 15-minutes long pitches and demos of the OSHW projects on an accessible video streaming platform. These video clips will be used for further dissemination by the consortium partners and the projects themselves. The internal workshops and training will be documented and the interactive tools (canvases, tasks, etc.) used in the workshops will be turned into a “Critical Maker Tools” booklet for any OSHW project to use to develop an RRI-informed practice.

As an additional resource that contributes to the open knowledge around OSHW and that will be used to engage the target groups we will compile a summary of guidelines on how to promote social responsibility as part of open hardware development. The guidelines will be targeted to organisations promoting maker activities and will be published as an easy to access online publication.

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PRINCIPLES

In our communication strategy, we aim to reach researchers, makers, the general public, corporations and start-ups, especially from the open hardware community, policy makers, the press and the general public. We think it is important to have the same principles from our projects reflect in our communication. Therefore, our project communication principles are also based on the Principles for Responsible Making.³

- Make Things that make sense: all our communication will be aligned with the RRI and Critical Making ideas, and our tone of voice will always be inclusive.
- Integrate Local Knowledge: we will make sure to always integrate all partners and participants in the communications efforts. At the same time making sure we understand the needs and the risk for other projects to be part of it.
- Include Ecosystem Services: We aim to give back more than what we can gain from this project.
- Build For Continuity and Share How You Make: All that will be developed in this project will be shared to help future projects and all the maker community.

³ Nuesse and Wanalo, 2020: <https://wellbeingeconomy.org/how-can-maker-spaces-boost-sustainability-and-help-build-a-wellbeing-economy>

These principles of responsible making will reflect our idea of what is a Critical Communication and Dissemination. We will make it to be open, gender and age friendly.

VISUAL IDENTITY

Our logo works as a stamp for nearly everything. When in doubt — always use this. It’s important to use the image with the name Critical Making when our brand is less known or it’s the first time showing it.

Figure 3: Critical Making Logo

Colours

We have two types of colour adopted in the visual identity, the Logo colours and the complementary (other) colours. We should only use these colours (plus white and black) on any visuals related to our project. (including presentations, social media, art, etc...)

Table 4. Brand Colours

Type	Colour	CMYK	RGB
Logo		9/8/35/11	209/201/160
Logo		88/36/49/19	0/112/114

Logo		100/80/17/0	19/78/143
Other		50/8/52/19	112/159/125
Other		53/74/21/0	139/93/142
Other		0/0/0/66	117/118/181
Other		100/95/5/0	43/57/144

Font

The primary font chosen for this project is Sans Pro, which is an open-source typeface family. This font is free for personal and commercial use, distributed under the SIL Open Font License.

Templates

Critical Making intends to use a consistent ‘project style’. This is implemented by providing templates for deliverables and reports, presentations, posters and other dissemination and communication material. More project-style templates can be produced by the communication and outreach team when needed.

All available project style templates are available on the shared workspace on the ZSI-hosted Nextcloud.

CHANNELS

We produced a website for the project under this domain: <http://criticalmaking.eu/>. Our Website structure is:

- About us & About the partners
- Projects
- Stories & Announcements e.g.:
 - Resources (Related Projects, Own Deliverables & Publications, Recommended Reading/Media)
 - Activity announcements
 - About Board information

Our strategy for other channels was to create a Twitter account (@critical_making) and use other partners' existing channels for our dissemination and where possible refer back to our common hashtag #criticalmaking. The following channels listed by Partners are available for our communications (Table 5):

Table 5. Partners Social Media

Partners	Website	Newsletter	Facebook	Linkedin	Instagram	Twitter
WIF	Story	✓	✓	✓	stories	✓
GIG	News section	✓, quarterly	✓	✓	✓	✓
VTT	Blog posts	✓	✓	✓	posts	✓
TUB	project description	no	no	no	no	✓
ZSI	News section	✓	✓	✓	Not sure	✓

The number of posts we plan to do you can see in the KPI table (table 9).

PRINT

As for now and due to the COVID-19 pandemic still going on, we don't need any print material. In a short future, we can foresee the need to have print-on-demand materials for possible offline events planned. Even in the case that these events are taken online due to the uncertainty brought about by the Covid-19, we may still need to print materials for distribution for community engagement.

ACADEMIC PUBLISHING

Critical Making aims to contribute to academic knowledge production with very concrete deliverables, such as the Critical Making Evaluation Report as a scientific article from WP6 or the Special issue on Critical Making from WP7. In sum, we plan to come forward with 5 academic papers and 1 special issue in a journal or as a book. In addition, we plan to attend conferences and as a result, come forward with a series of conference papers and proceedings. Whilst this academic publishing goes a rather traditional avenue of dissemination, we want to make sure that we commit to our critical making principles. For this reason, we will make sure that for any of our publications we offer our engaged stakeholder or participants in co-design action etc. the possibility for co-authorship.

In addition, Critical Making wants to critically reflect on alternative dissemination and publishing formats, that go beyond the format of the traditional academic paper. Therefore, we also want to address academic outcomes in alternative formats, such as video, audiocasts, or other dissemination artefacts.

PRESS & MEDIA

Our strategy for the Media and press is mainly focused on our partners' network. Press releases are used to share and communicate news about important projects announcements to raise awareness for critical making as

an area. We will also target local media from the partners' countries and the other projects that will get involved.

EVENTS

Other channels for dissemination are face to face (online and offline) presentations and workshops. These presentations and workshops are directly targeting the stakeholder groups and will be taking place at local venues where the stakeholder groups gather. To further promote the project findings and ensure a wide academic reach the partners organise workshops at several conferences and events. A list of relevant events and communities to connect to are provided in the tables below.

Table 6. Internal Events

Activity	Month
Interactive Workshop: Exploring Critical Making (whole consortium)	M3
Co-Creation Workshops (WP3, WP4, WP5)	M3-12
Meet-ups and workshops (WP3, WP4, WP5)	M6-30
European Climate Pact event (WP5)	M6-30
Final conference preparation and realisation (whole consortium)	M30

Table 7. External Events

Event, Location	Scope and target audience	Date 2021
EASST and 4S conferences	Annual and bi-annual conferences from the STS community; A	6-9 October 2021
CHI	The ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems is the most prestigious	8-13 May 2021

	academic conference on Human-Computer Interaction; A, I, P	
C&T	Communities and Technologies Conference; biennial international conference for scholarly debate and research on the complex connections between communities and ICTs. A, P	21-25 June 2021
ESOF	EuroScience Open Forum: biennial, pan-European, general science conference dedicated to scientific research and innovation. A, P	4-10 July 2022
TIPIC conference	Annual conference of the Transformative Innovation Policy Consortium; at the intersection of innovation, policy and transformative change, A, P	21-22 September 2021
Living Knowledge Conference	Annual conference on collaborative research with and for communities, A, C	30 June - 2 July 2021
re:publica	One of the largest annual events on digital culture in the world with a focus on the future of the information society; C, A, P, I	20-22 May 2021
Maker faires	Worldwide family events to showcase the possibilities of the Maker Movement. C, A, P, I	Many dates
Fabconference	Annual conference by the Fab Foundation, for all Fab Labs to exchange experiences on innovations in digital fabrication. C, I	9 - 15 August 2021
Dutch Design Week	Largest design event in North Europe. DDW organises and facilitates exhibitions, lectures, debates and award ceremonies. I, C	16 - 24 October 2021

A- Academia, C- Civil Society, P-Policy Makers, Government, I - Industry, Business

If partners are organising or attending any event, they have to share this information before the event happens so that we can also promote it through our social media and website.

EVALUATION & MONITORING

Communication, engagement and dissemination activities will be carefully measured to ensure that its impact is maximized. We base our evaluation on qualitative and quantitative factors.

Our qualitative monitoring strategy focuses on feedback generated by our contact with the community. It could be via the events and workshops or via comments from our social media.

Our quantitative monitoring strategy focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data from our social media and Website statistics. The website of critical making is connected to Wikifactory's Google Analytics. From there we can extract data as traffic to the page. Also, we will track the number of attendees on the events we promote. All this data will be carefully documented and their impact on the participants will be evaluated in the frame of the evaluation WP7.

KPIs from Proposal

Our KPIs were defined on the proposal. We will keep track of social media stats by month.

Table 8. Social Media Stats

Twitter	Jan 2021	Feb 2021	Mar 2021	Apr 2021	May 2021	April 2019
Followers	8	18	50	x	x	x
Tweets	2	2	13	x	x	x
Impressions	330	1295	7854	x	x	x

Table 9. KPIs

#	KPI	Target
1	Number of Academic Papers	5 papers
2	Number of scientific issues in journal or book, edited	1 special issue
3	Number of Institutions reached, in the EU, globally	200 institutions
4	Number of Social Media and community channels entries	1000 entries
5	Number of people reached in communication about the project	25.000 people
6	Number of SwafS projects collaborating with Critical Making	10 projects
7	Number of participants involved in the total activities of Critical Making	500 people

CONCLUSIONS

Critical Making is a research project that is embedded in a very dynamic environment and at the same time taking place during very challenging times due to the Corona pandemic. Thus, our communication, engagement and dissemination plan has to be flexible and adaptable to changing conditions. Most of all, our own engagement activities that are planned as physical encounters need to be reconsidered according to the actual situation. However, considerations regarding the tools and means from communications and dissemination should reflect the needs of different target groups. We are thus aware that this is a working live document and that we are dynamically adapting and our engagement strategy according to the specific needs and through iterative learning. This is thus a dynamic process that will be reflected upon in future deliverables.